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Housing, land and property restitution after wars takes decades: Ukraine can change this.

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Introduction

Ukraine is poised to transform the process of housing, land and property (HLP) restitution and compensation after wars. The Russian invasion of Ukraine has displaced more than 13.5 million people (UNHCR 2023) and created massive destruction and damage to the country's HLP. Initial efforts at recovery along with counter-offensives have stabilized large areas of the country and liberated others, to which displaced Ukrainians are now beginning to return (Duggar 2022; Conkling 2022). The Ukrainian government faces the monumental task of getting millions of returnees back to their HLP and facilitating compensation for damage and destruction.

Engaging in large-scale HLP restitution/compensation in Ukraine will be a daunting process. When refugees and IDPs (internally dislocated persons) return, many will not be able to prove they are the rightful occupants of their HLP because their property records are missing, destroyed, inaccurate, or never existed (Myers and Panfil 2022). Ukraine's property registry is only 40 percent complete, meaning that more than half of the country does not have formal digitized records of their property rights. For them, the risk of losing paper documentation of varying usefulness (if they existed) can be high as they failed to take them as they fled, or they were destroyed along with their HLP or from Russian targeting of HLP offices and archives. Properties can also be occupied by others or transacted as a political tool in the conflict—the latter a disturbing reality in eastern Ukraine (Coynash 2019), particularly now that Russia has attempted annexation of eastern territories (Lonsdorf and Harbage 2022).

Experience in other countries has demonstrated that large-scale forced displacements can last decades and even generations as restitution/compensation efforts are not planned or implemented in a timely manner, or claims are difficult or impossible to file for significant segments of the dislocated population. During this time HLP can change hands multiple times and become illegally or legally held by others, including political elites or opposed ethnic, sectarian or religious groups. Meanwhile, the grievances of displaced families do not usually abate, but instead build over generations, sometimes leading to destabilizing movements (Fay and James 2009).

But despite the challenges it faces, Ukraine has the potential to transform postwar HLP restitution/compensation processes as currently practiced. With its digital sophistication, smartphone penetration, and a capable government willing to innovate, Ukraine might

become the first war-affected country in which millions of displaced citizens can return to their HLP quickly, be compensated promptly, and engage in timely reconstruction.

How to do this?

Ukraine's moves to start the legal, technical, social, diplomatic and financial processes of HLP restitution/compensation while the war is still underway could set a new, much needed standard. Such a start not only advances the extensive preparations needed for large-scale returns to HLP, but opening large numbers of claims prior to a war's end can have strategic peacebuilding utility. This can occur by making legal and financial accountability for HLP damage and destruction widely known, particularly among international legal and financial institutions. This then creates a liability, which if pursued forcefully, would then need to be dealt with in the context of peace negotiations, victory or defeat. Postwar reparations and other forms of repayment have a long history, even for victors (ORSI 2022; Dolzer 2002). Such a prospect could potentially discourage the targeting of civilian HLP for destruction and illegal transaction.

While Ukraine's initiatives are encouraging, other aspects of the country's approach need work. First, Ukraine must change the approach currently in its Compensation Law (MPU 2022), of deciding restitution/compensation cases one by one for the hundreds of thousands to millions that will need decisions. No country can effectively process such a magnitude of claims in this manner. Instead, it should embrace a mass claims process, where large numbers of similar cases are grouped into categories and a single legal or administrative decision is then applied to the entire category, as has been done elsewhere (Holtzmann and Kristjansdottir 2007).

Second, Ukrainians who don't have a formal property document must be allowed to use other forms of evidence to verify where they lived (Panfil and Mellon 2019). This includes renters (largely informal), undocumented populations such as the Roma, and others caught in the prolonged, confused and heavily corrupt transition of the property rights system from the Soviet model. Unfortunately Ukraine's Compensation Law is overly focused on the pre-eminence of optimal documentation. With more than half the country lacking formal digitized property titles, it's easy to imagine very large numbers of legitimate claims being rejected by a restitution/compensation process (which occurred in the east of the country after Russia's 2014 incursion), resulting in significant duress on a recovering economy and possible socio-political problems.

Using nontraditional evidence for property restitution is not new; the UN's 'Pinheiro Principles' encourages countries to accept a wide range of evidence regarding property claims after a war (FAO 2007). Large-scale HLP restitution/compensation processes elsewhere have used corroborating evidence such as electricity and water bills to successfully pursue HLP claims (Holtzmann and Kristjansdottir 2007; IBPCA 2006). What is transformational now however is that such evidence is created constantly and in great variety and volume, just by virtue of living in the digital age—and the implications for HLP restitution are quite powerful. As more of the global population's social and economic lives move online, massive amounts of data are generated—such as Google

maps and phone location histories, e-commerce and rideshare receipts and digital utilities payments, among an array of other evidence. And in Ukraine, where two-thirds of the population owns a smartphone (Statista 2022), these records are available at one's fingertips.

Having evidence of property ownership, renting or occupation is one thing, but compiling and submitting that evidence quickly, simply and securely as part of a claim regardless of one's location is another. Ukrainians need a digital platform that allows them to file HLP claims remotely and in an encrypted manner. And claimants should be able to verify their identity and residency by being able to upload any evidence they have available, from audio testimonials to digital histories and photos. Once such a database is created it is then straightforward to screen out irrelevant, fraudulent or duplicate claims. The real problem is failing to upload relevant evidence due to narrow evidence rules, unawareness, or government over-reliance on the primacy of the optimal document in very fluid and chaotic institutional and socio-political settings.

Ukraine's Ministry of Digital Transformation has taken a critical step by reconfiguring its *Diia* digital services platform to allow citizens to file property damage claims; and already more than 240,000 have been submitted (Diia 2022). *Diia* could be improved however to take in a wider range of evidence and be encrypted. In any case such a digitized approach would enable far-flung claimants (refugees, IDPs) to file claims from any location, bypassing the arduous need to return to areas of origin to do this, which has been the case in most other conflicts. This facilitates starting the process before the war is over.

And finally, Ukraine needs a corruption-proof way of paying for all of this, ideally using money from seized Russian assets—with the Canadian government already having passed legislation to do this, and other countries underway with similar endeavours (Currie 2022; Moiseienko 2022). For dispensing such funds to claimants in ways that minimize corruption, one option would be to take a cue from the German Marshall Fund (Conley 2022) and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD 2022), and create a Ukraine Bank for Reconstruction and Development (UBRD). A UBRD could act as an independent entity whose purpose is to finance the restitution, rebuilding and repair of HLP.

To further head off the possibility of corruption, a digital voucher could be used as a form of compensation, as other claims processes have done. This allows claimants to only use the voucher to pay for repairs and re-building from verified contractors and suppliers. There is a wide variety of possibilities to use such a currency to tailor the remedy to the needs and desires of claimants (Humphreys 2015; FAO 2007).

Despite the obstacles it faces, Ukraine has all the tools to get this right: a highly educated and technically sophisticated population, an advanced digital infrastructure, and a government that is ready to move quickly and willing to listen to new ideas. With a bit of planning, Ukraine has the potential to become a model for a much more rapid, efficient, transparent and just post-war HLP restitution and reconstruction process.

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